

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE ACTION OF SOME CHEMICAL AND NATURAL SUBSTANCES ON CANDIDA ALBICANS CULTURES

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Abstract

In the present study, we followed for 96 hours the effectiveness of some chemical compounds proposed for the treatment of *Candida albicans*, more precisely: essential oils of: ginger, lemon, frankincense and neem, cedar, wormwood, Siberian cedar oil, magnesium oil, tincture of iodine 2 %, 2 solutions of sodium bicarbonate, apple cider, apple cider vinegar, iodized salt, citric acid as well as four solutions (samples) of 1M acetic acid.

Keywords: *Candida albicans*, culture medium, culture plates, *Candida Spp.*, essential oil, tincture

Abbreviations: h- hour; ATCC – standard culture of *Candida albicans*; µl - microliters; ml-milliliters; PS – physiological serum; 1M – molar concentration (1 mol/L; where L = liter).

Introduction

Candida albicans is a single-celled fungus from the yeast group, which in healthy people can act as a saprophyte of the digestive tract. *Candida tropicalis* is less common. Contamination with the fungus can be done through direct contact with the patient or through shared objects (1). Recent studies carried out in Europe and the USA highlight the increase in the incidence of nosocomial fungal infections, with a worrying mortality rate, which can reach 40-70% of cases. Fungiemiias due to various species of *Candida* are ranked 4th, in terms of incidence, in the list of systemic infections associated with medical care, after bacteremias with species from the genera *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Enterococcus* (2), (3).

Candida albicans is a commensal of the digestive tract and vagina. Depending on the location, it is classified into: cutaneous candidiasis; mucous candidiasis; nail candidiasis (candidal onychomycosis).

Cutaneous candidiasis affects in order of frequency: intertriginous regions, periorificial skin, fingers (4).

Candidal onychomycoses are nail lesions caused by nail infections with yeast fungi belonging to the genus *Candida*. The species most commonly found in nail parasites is *Candida albicans*. Other less frequently isolated species are *Candida guilliermondi*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Candida zeylanoides*, *Candida krusei* or *Candida parapsilosis* (5).

Factors favoring infection include prolonged antibiotic therapy, immunosuppressive therapy, diabetes,

AIDS, use of contraceptives, antitrichomoniasis treatment (6). *Candida* infections can be superficial or invasive; superficial infections often affect the skin or mucous membranes and can be successfully treated with topical antifungal medications. However, invasive fungal infections are often life-threatening, probably due to ineffective diagnostic methods and inadequate initial antifungal therapies (7), (8).

Invasive candidiasis is usually caused by dissemination of endogenous *Candida* species colonizing the patient's gastrointestinal tract. The risk for invasive candidiasis is higher during the early posttransplant period because of neutropenia, severe mucositis, and the presence of a central venous catheter (9).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was conducted over 4 days between August 25 and 30, 2019 at the "Provita 2000 Medical Center" Clinic in Constanța. The purpose of the study was to investigate the action of some natural products on *Candida Albicans* colonies. For this, we used Sabouraud standard culture medium, on which we seeded samples of *Candida albicans*, from a standardized assortment, called ATCC. We introduced the plates to the thermostat, at the standard temperature of 37 °C (10). In the present study, we carried out several experiments during 96 hours, using both natural products (essential oils, tinctures, etc.) and chemical products (sodium bicarbonate, citric acid, iodized salt), in order to be able to follow the action of the chemical compounds on *Candida albicans* cultures. The chemical compounds that were analyzed in the study were prepared in different dilutions. We then analyzed the size of the diameter of the zones of inhibition and lysis of the mycelial colonies at different time intervals (at 24 h, 48 h, 72 h (10) and at, 96 h).

Results

In this study, we investigated the action on candida of some essential oils: ginger, lemon, frankincense and neem, cedar, wormwood, magnesium oil, Siberian cedar oil, tincture of iodine 2 %, sodium bicarbonate solutions, apple cedar, of apple cider vinegar, citric acid, as well as four solutions of 1M acetic acid, over a period of 96 hours. In the first phase, I made the necessary

dilutions, after which I added 2-3 colonies of *Candida* spp. I mixed and left them at the thermostat for about an hour. Later, from the emulsion obtained, I seeded on the Sabouroud plate and introduced the samples to the thermostat for 24 h, 48 h...96 h, reading the result for each case.

Fig. 1.a. Preparation of sodium bicarbonate, citric acid and iodized salt solutions; 2.b. Preparation of 1M acetic acid solutions

96 h experiment (4 days)

a. In the first experiment I used apple cider, apple vinegar, iodized salt and citric acid. To prepare the citric acid solution, I dissolved 5 g of the substance (citric

acid) in 20 ml physiological serum. Apple cider and apple cider vinegar were used as they were commercially available. The iodized salt solution was prepared from 5 g of iodized salt and 20 ml of saline.

Fig 2. Culture plate seeded with *Candida albicans* and apple cider, apple vinegar, citric acid and iodized salt at 24 h (Fig 2.a) and 48 h (Fig. 2. B)

For apple cider and apple vinegar we observed sensitivity in the first 24 h after sowing.

Fig.3.a. Petri dish seeded with *Candida albicans* and apple cider, apple cider vinegar (fig. 5 a and b), citric acid and iodized salt at 72 h (fig 3.a and b)

Fig. 4.a. Petri dish seeded with *Candida albicans* and apple cider, apple vinegar, citric acid and iodized salt at 96 h (fig 4.a); Petri dish seeded with *Candida albicans* and apple cider, apple vinegar at 96 h (fig.4.b)

After 48 h, candida reappears in the case of the 4 substances used in the study; there is sensitivity to apple cider vinegar at 48 h and after, but not completely.

b. Sodium bicarbonate: 5 g/ 20 ml physiological serum, respectively 10 g/ 20 ml physiological serum. 2 % tincture of iodine was used in its native state.

Figure 5(a, b, c). Culture plate seeded with tincture of iodine (a, c) as well as sodium bicarbonate solutions at 24 h (a), 48 h (b), 72 h (c)

For sodium bicarbonate solutions no action appears against *Candida albicans* colonies in the first 4 days of incubation. The tincture of iodine proved very active on the *Candida* colonies during the 4 days.

Figure 6 (a, b, c). Petri plate seeded with *Candida albicans* with solutions of sodium bicarbonate (a, b) and tincture of iodine at 96 h (Fig 6.a, c)

c. Acetic acid 1M

For the experiment with acetic acid I prepared in the first phase 4 solutions/ samples of 1 M acetic acid (see table no. 1 and figure 1.b).

Table I. Composition of microbiologically analyzed acetic acid samples (used in the study)

Crt no	Samples	Acetic acid 1M (ml)	Physiological serum (ml)	Volumetric ratio (Acetic acid/ PS)
1.	I	1	5	1/ 5
2.	II	2	5	2/5
3.	III	3	5	3/5
4.	IV	4	5	4/5

Figure 7 (a, b, c, d). Culture plate seeded with *Candida albicans* on which the four solutions of 1M acetic acid were applied at 24 h (a), 48 h (b), 72 h (c) and 96 h (d), respectively

24 h after *Candida* seeding is observed a certain sensitivity for solutions / samples II, III and even IV of 1 M acetic acid, but not enough. The acetic acid used for the 48h, 72h and 96h, specifically samples III and IV has a degree of fungicidal action, but *Candida albicans* does not disappear permanently.

d. Siberian cedar oil (crude cold-extracted seed oil - for internal use), cedar essential oil, magnesium oil for massage (from Favisan), wormwood oil -200 µl oil /800 µl physiological serum

Figure 8(a, b, c, d) Culture plates seeded with *Candida albicans* on which oils of: Siberian cedar, cedar, magnesium and wormwood were applied in a concentration of 20% at 24, 48, 72 and 96 h

After 24 h, a degree of sensitivity occurs with cedar essential oil, unlike Siberian cedar oil for internal use. The four substances used in the experiment: Siberian cedar oil, cedar oil, wormwood oil and magnesium

oil were inactive on *Candida albicans*, for the 4 days of the experimental study.

e. Ginger, lemon, frankincense and neem oil-200 ml oil/800 ml physiological serum

Figure 9 (a, b, c, d, e.) Culture plate seeded with *Candida albicans* on which ginger, lemon, frankincense and neem oils were applied in a concentration of 20% at 24 h (a), 48 h (b,c), 72 h (d), 96 h (e)

In the case of ginger, frankincense and lemon oils, a fungicidal action occurs in the first 24 hours. After 48 h, the action is maintained only with the ginger oil, a little with the lemon oil and a little with the frankincense oil. With ginger oil, *Candida* did not reappear 72 h after sowing; also, with ginger essential oil, fungicidal action is also observed after 96 h, compared to neem oil, respectively, frankincense oil and lemon oil. Lemon oil and frankincense oil show a certain fungicidal action from the beginning, until the end of the 96 h; however, *Candida* continued to re-emerge in a very small amount with these substances 2 days after seeding.

Discussions

The dilutions of 200 μ l substance/800 μ l physiological serum were made for the essential oils, and the iodine tincture applied had a concentration of 2%. Apple cider and apple vinegar were sampled as they were commercially available. Iodized salt, sodium bicarbonate and citric acid were used in solutions (in liquid state). For acetic acid $\text{CH}_3\text{-COOH}$, 1 M, we made 4 different samples for the proposed study (see Table no.1). These substances were either in the form of tinctures, essential oils or other commercially available solutions. Over the solutions I added some colonies (2, 3) of *Candida* Spp. Apple cider and apple vinegar applied

in their native state show fungicidal action in the first 24 h, compared to the iodized salt solution and the citric acid solution used in the study. With tincture of iodine, an obvious fungicidal action is observed against *Candida albicans* and less with apple cider vinegar after 4 days after inoculation with *Candida albicans*. The sodium bicarbonate solutions used did not show fungicidal action against *Candida albicans*; proved ineffective at the concentrations used. In contrast, iodine tincture maintained its antifungal effect for the 4 days.

After 24 h of seeding, some fungicidal action is observed in samples III and IV of acetic acid, but not sufficient to inhibit the *Candida* colonies completely. Ginger, frankincense and lemon oil show a degree of fungicidal action in the first 24 hours compared to neem oil, as well as 48 hours after inoculation with *Candida albicans*. Also, after 72 h and 96 h, sensitivity appears to ginger oil, frankincense and a little to lemon oil compared to neem oil, which was not effective against *Candida*. It was observed that the four substances used in the experiment: Siberian cedar oil, cedar oil, wormwood oil and magnesium oil, were ineffective on *Candida albicans*, during the 4 days of the study, with the exception of cedar oil, which for 24 h showed fungicidal action against *Candida*. Oil of lemon and frankincense showed some sensitivity from the beginning until

the completion of 96 h, but candida continued to recur with these substances at the concentrations used. Apple cider vinegar used in food can be a prophylactic, but also curative remedy in the treatment of Candida. Candida albicans shows sensitivity for the first 24 h to ginger, frankincense and lemon oils and even more, for the 96 h from seeding to ginger, for dilutions of 200 µl substance/800 µl physiological serum. For this reason, the mentioned substances can have prophylactic and curative indications for Candida albicans. Tincture of iodine proved its antifungal effect for the 96 h of research.

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CONCLUSIONS

For apple cider vinegar, sensitivity of Candida colonies appears in the first 24 h compared to apple cider, iodized salt solution and citric acid. After 24 hours, a certain sensitivity of the Candida colonies to apple cider vinegar is observed, up to 96 hours of evaluation, but not completely; Candida reappears. The 2 sodium bicarbonate solutions we used in the study were found to be inactive in treating Candida. For the 4 days there is some sensitivity to samples III and IV of 1M acetic acid, but not enough to combat run. A higher concentration of acetic acid solutions; acetic acid which is commonly called vinegar could favorably influence the treatment of Candida albicans. A marked sensitivity of Candida colonies is observed for ginger oil and tincture of iodine, and a little for apple cider vinegar, after the 4 days of the study. Candida is totally sensitive to iodine tincture and ginger oil.

The results of the experiments reveal the fact that to treat mycoses of the skin and mucous membranes, we can use plant extracts (tinctures or oils) that can be applied locally. Thus, ginger oil is recommended, which showed a maximum fungicidal effect on Candida albicans colonies after 96 hours of incubation. The recommended concentration is 20%, in daily applications, until a total healing of the lesions.

Also, frankincense and lemon oil determine sensitivity of Candida colonies in the first 24 hours and, subsequently, to a lesser extent after 48 hours from seeding, up to 96 hours. We can consider that frankincense and lemon oil used in higher concentrations would give a good antifungal result or possibly by mixing them with other fungicidal substances. Lemon oil and frankincense oil can be used repeatedly/alternately with other antifungal substances.

Candida albicans is sensitive to apple cider vinegar, especially for the first 48 hours, and to a lesser extent thereafter. It could be used more often in food, with a prophylactic purpose. Iodine tincture and ginger oil showed their antifungal role in treating candida for the 4 days of the study.

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